

CARING ABOUT ENHANCED CURATION – WHAT, WHY, WHEN, HOW AND WHO?

Valentijn Gilissen

*DANS – Data Archiving and
Networked Services
The Netherlands
valentijn.gilissen@dans.knaw.n
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*[https://orcid.org/0000-0003-
2399-7598](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2399-7598)*

Abstract – Datamanagers at the Dutch repository for research data DANS recognize CoreTrustSeal Curation Levels in their work. These Curation Levels are seen as useful terminology to structure the workflow. A digital repository should arguably have strategies in place regarding file formats and actions may be taken by a datamanager during Enhanced Curation. These strategies aim to preserve datasets in a FAIR manner, even if the end users may not be aware of the needs for Enhanced Curation nor may seem to care for it. Enhanced Curation provides a clear focus for discussing file format strategies: *what* might be done, *why* to do it, *when* to take action, *how* to take action and *who* should preoccupy themselves with these matters.

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I. INTRODUCTION

DANS is the Dutch national centre of expertise and repository for research data [1]. In existence for 20 years and building on the work of predecessors, DANS has established itself as one of the leading repositories in Europe. Its Trusted Digital Repository services presently include four discipline-specific Data Stations which are built on the Dataverse software: the Data Stations Social Sciences & Humanities; Archaeology; Life Sciences and Physical & Technical Sciences [2]. DANS additionally manages

the technical infrastructure of DataverseNL for institutions wanting more direct management of their own Dataverse repository [3]. The DANS Data Stations contain over 300.000 datasets. While large collections of datasets are sent directly into the archive via a machine-to-machine protocol, many individual datasets continue to be manually deposited on a daily basis. These deposits are curated by the DANS Data Section: a team of datamanagers.

All of the work carried out by DANS is governed by protocols and policies, which are designed to conform to international standards of preservation such as the FAIR principles and the OAIS framework. The data curation workflow at DANS recognizes the distinction in Levels of Curation as defined by CoreTrustSeal: *Basic Curation* and *Enhanced Curation*. Basic Curation is performed on all manual deposits; datasets may be marked for Enhanced Curation when the datamanager deems this necessary for FAIR purposes. This paper will detail the workflow and further examine when and why Enhanced Curation should apply.

II. THE CURATION WORKFLOW AT DANS

CoreTrustSeal discerns the following levels of curation [4]:

A) *Content distributed as deposited*

B) Basic curation – e.g. brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation

C) Enhanced curation – e.g. conversion to new formats during ingest, enhancement of documentation and metadata

D) Data-level curation – as in C above, but with additional editing of deposited data

Curation level A is only recognized by DANS when it comes to machine-to-machine deposits. Such an automated ingest of datasets will however only be carried out after having carefully fine-tuned the process in a pilot project on a test server, to ensure that the datasets that are received are of sufficient FAIR-quality. DANS will always apply Basic Curation (level B) to manually deposited datasets. The full workflow is detailed in the DANS Data Processing Team Manual [5]. A datamanager will first perform a general appraisal of the dataset, to verify whether the dataset is a valid dataset that meets with the criteria of the DANS Selection Policy [6]. The dataset will also be checked for completeness as far as the datamanager can determine: if it contains all of the data files and documentation that can be expected. The dataset metadata is subsequently checked for erroneous use of fields, typos and omissions of fields which might still be easily added. As stated in the DANS Data Stations Policy [7], the metadata of a dataset may be adjusted by DANS for archiving purposes; to improve on the dataset's findability and clarity. The Rights Metadata are carefully checked to see if the depositor indicated the presence of personal data and took the appropriate measures for complying with the GDPR; the datamanager will additionally check the chosen licence and any restrictions placed on data files. While the depositor is ultimately responsible for ensuring proper management and handling of personal data, DANS will provide guidance on this topic and the datamanager will contact the depositor if they think that the settings are different from what may be necessary or desirable.

The dataset must include sufficient documentation to enable reuse. If the datamanager regards the documentation or data content as insufficient, the depositor will be contacted to provide additional information. Other than the initial appraisal, DANS will never interfere with the actual content of the data: the researcher is responsible for the content, the repository is responsible for the

long-term preservation and dissemination of the data. As such, Curation Level D is considered out of scope of the duties of the repository; it does not apply at DANS.

The datamanager will review the deposited data files and their organization. The file formats are evaluated according to the DANS Preferred Formats guidelines [8]; the organization is reviewed on clarity of folder structures and descriptions of names of files and folders. If non-preferred formats are present for which the datamanager does not have any tools available, or should the dataset content be too unclear for the datamanager; they will contact the depositor and discuss whether different formats may be deposited and if the content can be clarified. Should the datamanager have tools available to convert non-preferred formats to preferred formats, or if the datamanager can improve on the organization of the dataset themselves; they will mark the dataset in their administration for Enhanced Curation (Curation Level C). The datamanager will publish the dataset after (and only after) performing Basic Curation but before performing Enhanced Curation: Enhanced Curation will be added as a revision of the published dataset. This procedure retains the authenticity of the original deposit and provides provenance in the administration of the dataset. Datasets in Dataverse show a clear version history with version differences and show if the versions were created by the depositor or the archive. Users can access earlier versions; the persistent identifier (each dataset is assigned a DOI) will always lead to the most recently published version.

The workflow described above has matured over time and was adapted to working with the Dataverse software. DANS started with dataset archiving in 2005 in the self-built repository EASY, which was still in use until 2024 when DANS launched the last of its four discipline-specific Data Stations and migrated every dataset from EASY to the corresponding Data Station. EASY did not have a version feature for datasets and therefore datasets had to be fully completed before publication; subsequent edits on datasets were undesirable as the dataset could be referenced after publication and users should be able to rely on their references to remain authentic and unchanged. Any curation on file formats or file organization needed to be performed before publication; the original deposit was automatically

placed in a subfolder called 'original' and the datamanager would upload their file conversions or restructures outside of that folder. While manageable, this was never ideal. Depositors and datamanagers had long expressed a desire for a better versioning mechanism. Additionally, the datamanager having to complete the entire curation before publishing the dataset could often cause a long period of time between the moment of deposit and the moment of publication. The present workflow in Dataverse is much quicker and provides clearer provenance and authenticity. The different actions that might be performed on a dataset fit with the distinction in Curation Levels and using that terminology provides the datamanager with a structured workflow.

III. ENHANCED CURATION MATTERS

As detailed in the previous chapter, Enhanced Curation is performed in order to provide a dataset with Preferred Formats and/or a clearer structure. The use of robust and (as much as possible) open and standardized file formats is regarded as a main aspect of the Interoperability part of the FAIR-ness of a dataset; making use of widely used file formats increases the dataset Reusability [9]. Curation is seen as an aspect of preservation to ensure that data and will remain accessible, usable and understandable in the long term [10]. However, there are no universally agreed upon standards on preferred file formats and curation strategies. Many institutions dealing with digital preservation will have their own file format policy in place which is likely to overlap with other policies in some way, but there are many differences to be found across institutions [11].

DANS shares the view that file formats can still be in danger of falling into disuse and becoming unsupported; therefore long-term preservation should aim to make use of robust file formats. This view is partially informed by experience, such as with older Microsoft Access database formats (version 97 and prior) not being supported by the current version of the application; it is also supported by an analysis carried out by the Preservation Watch of the Dutch Digital Heritage Network on monitoring file format sustainability, which clearly showed transitions in file format usage and declines in the use of certain file formats [12] [13] [14]. To have as FAIR data as possible, DANS argues to aim to make as much use of preferred formats as possible. The

terminology 'accepted formats' should be avoided as this gives depositors the impression that such formats can be accepted as-is, while there may be preferred alternatives; the term 'accepted formats' also implies that there are 'non-accepted' formats which risks depositors deselecting data before submitting, resulting in incomplete datasets, DANS steers depositors to the use of preferred formats and may convert data during enhanced curation, but when options are limited non-preferred formats are still accepted with the acknowledgement that non-preferred formats make for less long-term guarantees. As detailed in chapter II, original data is retained in case of conversions to preserve the data as deposited. Besides reasons of authenticity, provenance and reproducibility of the research data, it may also be the case that data is deposited in file formats which are not ideal for long-term preservation but which are nevertheless current usage formats, desired by users for the time being. This could be the case with, for example, propriety Shapefiles or 3D data formats which require their original software for full usage; exports to more robust and interoperable formats may not retain all original properties.

Datamanagers may have software available to them to perform format conversions; they may however always encounter formats which they cannot access and where the depositor is unable to deliver alternative formats. The aim should be to perform Enhanced Curation as much as possible, but options can be limited. Ideally, data will be automatically converted to interoperable formats by the repository software, under supervision of the datamanager: Dataverse has such a feature available for statistical data formats. Developments of similar features for other data types would be ideal for the future of digital preservation.

IV. WHO CARES?

Research is supported by data and the strength of the supporting data is found in the manner in which it can be corroborated, reproduced, verified or falsified. A data repository should not be the final stop on the road of research. The scientific method; research and data management are often represented as ongoing cyclical processes; many representations can be found of a research data (life) cycle [15]. The repository plays a key role in facilitating this cyclical nature: it allows research data

to 'land' in a place where it can be found, referenced to and reused for new research. All of the effort in making data more FAIR is done to support the research cycle and to allow the wheels to keep turning.

The importance of these efforts; of Enhanced Curation, may not always be evident to the depositor or to the user. In December 2024, a DANS staff member met with a group of researchers involved in the creation of 3D data projects. They were asked if they considered preservation at the beginning of their projects. Nobody did, nor did they know what exactly needed to be preserved for their projects. The common conception was that it was the concern of someone else. A data management plan might help bring attention to the topic of preservation, but the researchers thought it impossible to plan for preservation within the flexible nature of their projects.

The discussion mentioned above is only one undocumented source regarding the position of the data depositor, but is it reasonable to expect different responses? After all, the data repository is likely to position itself as the center of expertise for preservation issues.

V. CONCLUSION

Illustrating the DANS workflow in the light of the CoreTrustSeal Curation Levels identifies Enhanced Curation as an active component of the processes taking place within the repository to improve on the FAIR quality of datasets. File format guidelines and data management plans may steer the input from depositors to the use of preferred formats but a repository may always expect to receive non-preferred formats: formats in danger of becoming obsolete. It is the role of the digital repository to identify when it is necessary to take action in regards to file formats. If the repository aims to make data available for reuse, they are best positioned to be the main actor when it comes to ensuring interoperability. This may often be a dialogue with the depositor, who may have software available to them that the repository does not. File format strategies certainly need to be informed by expert input from data users and communities, who possess knowledge on current usage formats, needs and preferences. The datamanager should also 'manage' this input and the available options on the basis of their expertise on preservation. Reliance on

depositors and users for input may mean that the datamanager should take an active role in illustrating the importance of the aims and goals of the repository; clarifying the reasons for curation may contribute to the recognition of the research data cycle, thereby support and strengthen its ongoing processes.

Clear showcases of reuse of research data may help in this regard, but it is the experience of DANS that good examples of reuse can be hard to find – the means to detect and show data reuse should therefore be a main concern for future developments.

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHY

Valentijn Gilissen works at the Dutch research data repository DANS as Data Processing Team Leader, Data Steward and Preservation Officer. He is responsible for preservation policies such as the DANS Preferred Formats guidelines. Valentijn is part of the Preservation Watch expert group of the Dutch Digital Heritage Network.

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